

A STUDY OF PRICE DISCOVERY PROCESS IN COMMODITIES MARKET IN INDIA: A CASE STUDY OF TURMERIC MARKET

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ABSTRACT:Price discovery is the process of determining the price of a commodity security or asset by competing buyers and sellers. The process of price discovery has gained considerable importance in commodity market as it is linked to informational efficiency and arbitrage strategies. This study analyses whether Turmeric futures market serves as a price discovery mechanism for spot market prices and vice versa. The analysis involves the use of econometric tools like Augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF), Granger Causality test and cointegration technique. The daily closing data from 1st April 2016 to 31st March 2018 have been used for the study. The study reveals the existence of price discovery mechanism in turmeric market, where spot markets are more efficient in discovering the price of turmeric.

KEY WORDS: Spot prices, Futures Prices, Turmeric, ADF test, Granger Causality test, Johansen's Cointegration

I. INTRODUCTION

Turmeric is one of the oldest spices and is being used in India for a long time. It is also called 'Indian saffron'. It is used in many Hindu rituals even now and Indians have a tendency to be attached to it emotionally. It is also an effective medicine for stomachaches and disorders. With this many applications, India is the largest producer, consumer and exporter of this spice. The world production of turmeric comes approximately 800000 tons out of which India holds a share of roughly 75-80%. India is also a biggest consumer of turmeric consumes around 80% of its own production. Turmeric holds a name of being auspicious in India. It has been used in India in many Hindu rituals and ceremonies. India is one of the largest producers of turmeric in the world. The largest state in India that produces turmeric is Andhra Pradesh. The production of turmeric exceeds the demand due to which India exports turmeric to other countries in the world. The turmeric produced in India is considered to be the finest quality turmeric in the world. The country exports around 40000 tons to the countries like United Arab Emirates, United States, Japan, United Kingdom and Sri Lanka.

II. TRADING OF TURMERIC IN INDIA

In India, turmeric is traded at

- Nizamabad
- Dugirala
- Sangli
- Salem
- Erode

- Dharmapuri
- Coimbatore

The turmeric futures contract are traded in India in the commodity exchanges like , National Commodity & Derivatives Exchange Ltd and The Spices and Oilseeds Exchange Ltd. Turmeric futures contract trading commenced on NCDEX platform in April 2004 and since then it has observed significant participation from various supply chain participants. By trading in commodity exchange platform, the traders and producers can minimize the price risk. With the increasing export demand; exporters can safe guard themselves against price risk. Ample stocks of Turmeric offer good arbitrage prospect to the various market participants. Since turmeric futures are a highly liquid contract speculators are able to easily enter or exit the market. This ensures that the Turmeric contract provides space for every investor category.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Prassanna (2014) made a performance evaluation of Agricultural commodity futures market in India. The study have used ten agricultural commodities (Barley, Chan, Castor seed, Soyabean, Potato, Guar gum, Guarseed, Jeera, Pepper, Turmeric) for the study. The study used Johansen's cointegration test, Granger causality and VECM to measure the performance of these commodities. The depth of the market is measured by the number of contracts traded. The study revealed that Barley, Castor seed, Jeera and pepper have their spot market leading to future market in price discovery because of the low participation in futures market. Chana is having high level of participation, which reflects in future market which leads the spot market for price discovery. Guar gum, Guarseed, even though have high participation, spot prices leads to futures because of frequent bans and abnormal trading due to unprecedented demand. Soyabean is considered as an international commodity an international commodity and for turmeric futures market is not explained by the participation level in futures market. Thus the study concluded that the strength of futures market is weak in many commodities

Shakeel and Purankar (2014) studied the price discovery mechanism of three top traded agricultural commodities on NCDEX viz; Soybean, Castor seed and chana. The Johansen's cointegration test revealed that there is a long run equilibrium relationship between spot and futures prices of the variables. The VECM results revealed that there is bidirectional causality between spot and futures market of the selected commodities and these commodities are said to be informationally efficient and reacts quickly to each other.

Krithiga and Azhagaiah(2014) studied the linkages among 12 agricultural commodities (Barley, Castor seed, Chana, Coriander, Cotton seed oilcake, Jeera, Mustard seed, Refined soyoil, Soybean, Sugar, Turmeric & Wheat) and their cross hedging possibilities in India. Karlpearson's Correlation is used to find the relationship between the commodities and it has been found that all the commodities ar related and are affected by micro economic factors. Further long run and short run equilibrium relationship among the commodities is confirmed through ECM. The study revealed that commodities of same category show a significant relationship with futures prices of selected commodities of that category. Further the selected agricultural commodities which are grown in same area and same season have strong relationship with futures prices of other selected commodities. The study concluded that hedgers can use futures contract of one commodity to hedge against the other commodity based on the same category

Yagati and Kamaiah (2012) studied the hedging efficiency of commodities future market in India. Redchilly, Jeera, Pepper and turmeric from NCDEX, cardamom from MCX and base metals from MCX have been taken into consideration. OLS regression model and error correction model have been used in the study. The study found that Red chilly is having hedge ratio and hedging effectiveness higher than Jeera, pepper and turmeric. The study found out that cardamom's hedging performance is poor due to low volume of trade. The study concluded that hedging efficiency of base metals is high compared to agricultural commodity futures

Singhal et.al (2011) studied the impact of commodity trading on volatility of commodity spot prices by taking into consideration 3 commodities viz; sugar, chana and turmeric traded in NCDEX during the period 01/01/2010 to 31/12/2010. The study used correlation, regression and granger causality tests. Garch (1, 1) model was used to study the volatility. The study revealed that there is no sufficient evidence that shows future market leads to inflation

From the reviews it can be seen that even though there are many studies relating to price discovery in commodities market, studies on agricultural commodities in spices genre is less. Hence the study has been taken up.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyze the price discovery process of Turmeric future and spot price contacts

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on secondary data. Secondary data of futures and spot price of turmeric are collected from 01/01/2014 to 31/12/2015. All the data are obtained from MCX Website. The study used Augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF Test) to check the stationarity of data. Granger Causality test is used to find the nature and existence of causality between the variables. The long term relationship between futures and spot price is found out using cointegration technique.

4.1 AUGMENTED DICKEY FULLER TEST

An Augmented Dickey Fuller Test is used to assessment for the incidence of unit root in a time series.

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma y_{t-1} + \delta_1 \Delta y_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta y_{t-p+1} + \varepsilon_t,$$

where α is a constant, β the coefficient on a time trend and p the lag order of the autoregressive process. Imposing the constraints $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta = 0$ resembles to displaying a random walk and using the constraint $\beta = 0$ resembles to exhibiting a random walk with a drift.

4.2 GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST

The granger causality test is a statistical hypothesis test that is helpful to find out if one time series is beneficial to forecast the other. In general, regressions reproduce "simple" correlations, then Clive Granger claimed that causality in economics could be tested for by computing the competence to forecast the future values of a time series by means of past values of another time series. When time series X Granger-causes time series Y , the patterns in X are almost repeated in Y after some time lag. Thus, past values of X can be used for the calculation of future values of Y .

4.3 JOHANSEN'S COINTEGRATION TEST

In statistics, the Johansen test, called after Søren Johansen, is a technique for testing cointegration of several, say k , $I(1)$ time series. The null hypothesis for the trace test is that the number of cointegration vectors is $r < k$, vs. the alternative that $r = k$.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 RESULTS OF AUGMENTED DICKEY FULLER TEST

Table : 1 Augmented Dickey Fuller test results

	Spot at level	Spot at 1st differencing	Futures at level	Futures at 1st differencing
<i>ADF test statistic</i>	-1.841	-9.695	-2.312	-20.793
<i>P Value</i>	0.361	0.000	0.168	0.000
<i>Conclusion</i>	Non Stationary	Stationary	Non Stationary	Stationary

Source: Author's Calculation

The results disclose that all the variables are non stationary at level. But they are found to be stationary at their first difference. Therefore necessary condition for cointegration is satisfied.

5.2 RESULTS OF JOHANSEN’S COINTEGRATION TEST

Table: 2 Johansen’s cointegration test results

Hypothesized	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic			Max-Eigen Value		
		Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.048689	24.23145	15.49471	0.0019	22.16174	14.26460	0.0023
At most 1	0.004651	2.069707	3.841466	0.1502	2.069707	3.841466	0.1502

Source: Author’s Calculation

The table 2 reveals that there is at most 1 cointegrating vector between future and spot prices of turmeric. This shows that both future and spot prices have long run equilibrium relationship with each other and move together in long run. This confirms the price discovery in turmeric market. After confirming the cointegration, granger causality test is performed to know the direction of causality between the spot and future market of turmeric.

5.3 RESULTS OF GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST

Table 3: Results of Granger Causality Tests

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
Spot price does not granger cause Future price	447	13.120	0.000
Future price does not granger cause Spot Price		5.540	0.004

Source: Author’s Calculation

Granger causality test reveals that there is a bi directional causality relationship between future price and spot price of turmeric. As the coefficient of “spot prices does not granger causes future prices” is higher in magnitude it shows a domination of spot market compared to future market in Turmeric market, where the information or shock is first reflected in spot market which is then reflected in future market. Thus shows that spot prices of turmeric can be useful to predict the future prices of turmeric. The results confirm that price discovery function of copper market is done by SPOT MARKET.\

VII. CONCLUSION

Johansen’s Cointegration technique along with Granger Causality Test has been employed to study the price discovery of futures and spot price in turmeric traded in NCDEX for a period 1st April 2016 to 31st March 2018. The empirical analysis was done on the daily time series during the period. Using ADF test, it was found that all the variables are stationary at their first difference. Johansen’s Cointegration test revealed there is a long run equilibrium relationship between the futures and spot prices. The price discovery is further confirmed by granger causality test, where the coefficient of “spot prices do not granger causes future prices” is higher in magnitude. This confirms a domination of spot market in turmeric. So, study concludes that spot prices can be more useful to predict future prices and price discovery function is done predominantly in spot market.

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